

BioMedIT: Switzerland's Trusted Research Environment

A project of

Sensitive health data research dilemma

Swiss Health ecosystem generates massive sensitive health data from clinical trials, genomics, and real-world evidence. However, critical barriers are impeding its research:

- Data privacy and security concerns limiting collaborative research
- Regulatory compliance complexity slowing analysis workflows
- Interoperability issues between different data systems
- Need for trusted infrastructure supporting multi-institutional studies

What BioMedIT offers

BioMedIT is a Federated Trusted Research Environment (fTRE)

- Supports Secure Processing Environments
- Offers additional secure services
- Manages entry and exit from fTRE
- Manages AAI and groups

Coordinates:

- Security
- ITSM
- Technology and tools
- Incidents
- Operations
- Data interoperability

A secure IT network for the responsible processing of health-related data.

BioMedIT: Switzerland's Trusted Research Environment

- Secure cloud and HPC offerings
 - Central [IT Service] Coordination(SIB)
 - 3 physical nodes (at Swiss Universities) providing scientific IT support
 - BioMedIT Portal as entry point, central tools and services
 - Security by design: Common Information Security Policy (Swiss standard)
- Secure mobilization, processing and storage of sensitive research data
- End-to-end encrypted data transfers (via sett)

>BIO MED IT< National Landscape

- > 120 Projects
- > 1000 Registered Users
- 33 Data Providers
- Secure Compute
 - 10 K+ Cores
 - 5 PB+ Storage
 - 350+ GPUs

BioMedIT

Current Architecture: 3 Federated Nodes

E
r

Central Services

Terminology Service

SPHN DCC
Confluence

Schema Forge
SPHN Schema Forge

SPHN
Federated Query System

GitLab

>BIOMED IT< >BIOMED IT<

sett Portal

Portal git

Tools & Resources

ire

Researchers

Access 2FA

Additional Software & Containers

Security Check

BioMedIT Node

Inter-Node Connection

BioMedIT B-Spaces: Typical Architecture

